

Studies in Ring Formation. Part III. The Condensation of Benzidine with Dibasic Acid Anhydrides.

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In continuation of the preceding work the present paper deals with the constitution of the products obtained by the condensation of benzidine with dibasic acid anhydrides in general.

Naphthalic, camphoric, quinolinic, and diphenic anhydrides have now been condensed with benzidine and it has been found that wherever the reaction takes place between one molecule of the anhydride and one molecule of the diamine, only one amino group of the latter body takes part in the reaction—the other amino group remaining free. The presence of the free amino group is proved in each case by the fact that the reaction products can (a) condense with a molecule of an aldehyde and (b) be diazotised and coupled with a second component.

It is thus definitely established that in the reaction between one molecule of any dibasic acid anhydride and one molecule of benzidine a compound of the type—

as suggested by Koller (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2880) and accepted by Kauler (*Annalen*, 1907, 351, 151) in the case of mono-phthalyl benzidine, is never formed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Naphthalyl-benzidine,

Naphthalic anhydride (1 g.) and benzidine (1 g.) were finely powdered and thoroughly mixed in a mortar, 50 c.c. of water added and the mixture was heated in a suspended condition under reflux for about 15 minutes. Water was decanted off from the fused mass which solidified on cooling. It crystallised from hot pyridine in beautiful, yellow needles, m. p. above 300°.

It is insoluble in alcohol or benzene sparingly soluble in acetic acid but easily soluble in hot pyridine or nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in dilute acids or alkalis. It readily condenses with aldehydes and can be diazotised and coupled with phenolic bodies. (Found: N, 8·18. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2N_2$, requires N, 7·69 per cent.).

Dinaphthalyl-benzidine.—An intimate mixture of naphthalic anhydride (2 g.) and benzidine (0·9 g.) was heated in a test tube on the oil-bath at 250° for 3-4 hours. The resultant product crystallised from boiling pyridine in golden yellow needles, not melting below 300°.

It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene or acetic acid, but soluble in boiling pyridine or nitrobenzene. It does not dissolve in dilute acids or alkalis and does not condense with aldehydes. (Found: N, 5·18. $C_{36}H_{20}O_2N_2$, requires N, 5·14 per cent.).

Benzylidene-naphthalyl-benzidine,

The crystals which separated on heating a mixture of naphthalyl-benzidine (0·5 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 c.c.) in pyridine (20 c.c.) for 10 minutes, were further purified by re-crystallisation from hot pyridine. It forms light-yellow, glistening plates melting at 297°.

It is insoluble in benzene, alcohol or acetic acid but soluble in pyridine or nitrobenzene. It is easily hydrolysed into its constituents. (Found: N, 6·55. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2N_2$, requires N, 6·19 per cent.).

Salicylidene-naphthalyl-benzidine was prepared from salicylic aldehyde (1 c.c.) and naphthalyl-benzidine (0·5 g.) in the same way and possesses properties similar to the preceding compound.

It forms rectangular, greenish-yellow plates melting at 288°, and does not dissolve in caustic alkalis. (Found: N, 5·95. $C_{31}H_{20}O_2N_2$, requires N, 6·00 per cent.).

m-Nitro-benzylidene-naphthalyl-benzidine was prepared from naphthalyl-benzidine (0.5 g.) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 g.) in the same way as the preceding compound. It forms beautiful, yellow hexagonal prisms melting at 299°, and in its properties resembles the two previous compounds. (Found: N, 8.82. $C_{31}H_{16}O_4N_3$ requires N, 8.45 per cent.).

Camphoryl-benzidine.—A mixture of camphoric anhydride (1 g.) and benzidine (4.5 g.) was heated under suspension in 100 c.c. of water for 10 minutes. The contents were filtered hot and the residue freed from unreacted benzidine by boiling with water and filtering hot. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in fine colourless, clustering needles, m. p. 190°.

It is fairly soluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in hot water, dilute acids or alkalis but insoluble in sodium carbonate solution. It easily condenses with aldehydes and can also be diazotised and coupled with phenols. (Found: N, 8.19. $C_{22}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 8.04 per cent.).

Quinoliny-benzidine.—A mixture of quinolinic anhydride (0.73 g.) and benzidine (0.96 g.) suspended in 50 c.c. of benzene was heated under reflux for 10 minutes. The separated solid was treated with alcohol, to remove any unreacted material, and finally crystallised from nitrobenzene as light yellow, rectangular prisms, m. p. above 300°.

It is insoluble in alcohol, acetic acid, dilute acids or alkalis, but soluble in nitrobenzene. (Found: N, 13.51. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

The crude product before crystallisation readily dissolves in dilute alkali and sodium carbonate solutions. This is perhaps due to the fact that at first an additive compound, *viz.*, *p*-amino-diphenyl-quinolinamic acid—

is formed which in the process of crystallisation loses a molecule of water and is transformed into quinoliny-benzidine.

p-Amino-ditolyl-quinolinamic acid.—A mixture of quinolinic anhydride (0.75 g.) and tolidine (1 g.) suspended in benzene (60 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 15 minutes. The separated solid was washed with benzene and finally crystallised from nitrobenzene in brilliant yellow needles, melting at 281°.

It is insoluble in alcohol, acetic acid or benzene but soluble in nitrobenzene. It dissolves in dilute alkali and sodium carbonate solutions. (Found: N, 11.63. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_3$ requires N, 11.63 per cent.)

N. B.—No quinolinyl-tolidine was obtained in this case (*cf.* the preceding experiment).

p-Amino-diphenyl-diphenaminic acid.—The solid which separated on refluxing for 15 minutes a mixture of diphenic anhydride (1.1 g.) and benzidine (0.9 g.) suspended in benzene (50 c.c.) was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol.

It forms microscopic crystals, m. p. 199°. It is insoluble in benzene or dilute acids, but soluble in alcohol, dilute alkali or sodium carbonate solutions. (Found: N, 6.35. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.86 per cent.)

The compound could not be made to lose a further molecule of water and form a ring, which would evidently be seven-membered.